

THE ROLE OF METAPHORS IN LANGUAGE AND THOUGHT: INSIGHTS FROM CHINESE, ENGLISH, AND UZBEK

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Annotation: This paper analyses the metaphors used in Yu Hua’s novel *To Live* and how they are translated into Uzbek and English. The study focuses on linguistic and semantic transformations that occur during translation and the cultural adaptation of metaphors. The research identifies translation strategies such as direct equivalence, cultural adaptation, and neutralisation, examining their impact on meaning transmission. The study highlights the challenges translators face in conveying metaphors across different linguistic and cultural contexts.

Keywords: metaphor, Yu Hua, *To Live*, linguistics, semantics, translation studies, cultural adaptation.

1.1. Metaphor in Literary Translation

Metaphors play a crucial role in literary texts by enriching imagery and deepening meaning.¹ According to Lakoff & Johnson, metaphors are not merely rhetorical devices but fundamental structures of human thought.² However, translating metaphors poses a significant challenge due to differences in linguistic structures and cultural perceptions across languages Newmark.³

Gulnoza Odilova, in her work *Functional Styles of Translation*,⁴ states that metaphor translation should consider functional stylistic equivalence, where

¹Baker. M. (1992). *In Other Words: A Coursebook on Translation*. Routledge.

²Lakoff, G. & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors We Live By*. University of Chicago Press.

³Newmark. P. (1988). *A Textbook of Translation*. Prentice Hall.

⁴Odilova. G. (2024). *Theory of translation*.

metaphors must be adapted according to the stylistic norms of the target language. In some cases, she argues, metaphors may require cultural reinterpretation to maintain their effect in translation.

1.2. Research Objectives

This study aims to:

Identify and analyze metaphors into Live and their translations into Uzbek and English.

Examine the linguistic and cultural shifts in metaphor translation.

Evaluate translation strategies used in transferring metaphors.

Discuss the challenges of preserving metaphorical meaning in translation.

Metaphor translation has been widely studied in translation theory. Newmark (1988) categorizes metaphor translation into three main strategies:

1. Direct Equivalence – Retaining the original metaphor if it exists in the target language.

2. Cultural Substitution – Replacing the metaphor with a culturally relevant equivalent.

3. Neutralization – Replacing the metaphor with a literal or explanatory phrase.

Baker emphasizes the role of cultural background in metaphor translation, arguing that some metaphors are culture-specific and may not be easily transferable without adaptation.

Venuti introduces the concepts of domestication (adapting the text to fit the target culture) and foreignization (keeping the original cultural elements intact).

The table below presents metaphors from the original Chinese text, their English and Uzbek translations, and the translation strategies used.

余华 "活着"	Yu Hua "To live"	Yuy Xua "Yashamoq"
我如同一只乱飞的麻雀。 (4)	I was like a sparrow soaring recklessly.(4)	Insiz qolgan chumchuqday kezib yurardim. (5)
突然发现自己像个孕妇一样步履艰难了。(4)	I had as much difficulty walking as a pregnant woman . (4)	Qornim homilador ayollanikiday shishib , birqadam ham tashlay olmaydigan holga kelib qolibman. (6)

<p>"做人呵,一旦嫖上以后,也就免不了要去赌。这个嫖和赌,就像是胳膊和肩膀连在一起,怎么都分不开。" (9)</p>	<p>Once the day comes that a man starts to go whoring, gambling can't be too far behind. Whoring and gambling are just like a pair of arms or legs: inseparable. (Page 11)</p>	<p>Xom sut emgan banda, yengiltak ayollarga birmarta ilakishdingmi, albatta, qimorxonaga ham tanda qo'yasan. (14)</p>
<p>"我丈人当时的脸就和松花蛋一样,我呢,嘻嘻笑着过去了。(9page)</p>	<p>As I asked, my father-in-law's face would look like a preserved egg. Me, I'd just giggle and continue on my way. (Page 13)</p>	<p>Unga shunday deganimda qaynotamning yuziburishibketar; men bo'lsam qiqir-qiqir kulgancha yo'lda davom etardim. (17-bet)</p>
<p>"我当时冷冷地说了一句: '你是不是风一吹就要倒呀?'"(page 9)</p>	<p>"Look at you. As soon as the wind blows your stomach doubles in size." (page 11)</p>	<p>Unga sovuqgina qilib: «Yoningdan shamo lo'tib ketsa ham boshqorong'i bo'lib qolasan-a?», degandim o'shanda. (16)</p>
<p>我骑在妓女身上经过他的店门时,我丈人身手极快,像只耗子呼地一下窜到里屋去了。(10 page)</p>	<p>When I passed his shop riding on that whore's back, my father-in-law would be startled into retreat — like a rat scurrying back into his little hole. (Page 14)</p>	<p>Biror yengiltak ayol bilan do'koni oldidan o'tayotganimni ko'rib qolsa, mushukdan qo'rqib, iniga qochgan sichqonday g'oyib bo'lardi.(18-bet)</p>
<p>"男人都是馋嘴的猫。" (12 page)</p>	<p>Men are nothing but a bunch of gluttonous cats." (page 17)</p>	<p>"Erkaklar ochofat mushukka o'xshaydilar" (21-bet)</p>
<p>一听这话眼睛就眯成了两条门缝 (13)</p>	<p>As soon as he heard this his eyes squinted like two little peepholes. (16)</p>	<p>Bu so'zlarni eshitishi bilan hayratdan ko'zlari olayib, tirjaya boshladi. (22)</p>
<p>家珍的脑袋像是拨郎鼓那样摇晃了几下。(16)</p>	<p>Her head swayed back and forth like a toy rattle.(22)</p>	<p>Boshi o'yinchoq misoli yon va ortga tebranib ketdi. (28)</p>
<p>看着凤霞哭,我心里就跟刀割一样。(21)</p>	<p>Seeing Fengxia cry was like having a knife pierce my heart. (28)</p>	<p>Fengxiyaning bu holini ko'rib, qalbinga xanjar sanchilgandek bo'ldi.(36)</p>

凤霞这么小的年纪就知道护着她爹，就是看着这孩子，我也该千刀万剐。(21)	Just looking at her made me feel like I deserved to be cut to pieces. (28)	Uni shu ahvolda ko'rgandan ko'ra, parcha- parcha bo'lib titilib, yo'q bo'lib ketsam bo'lmasmidi? (36)
"一大把年纪全活到狗身上去了。" (32)	"Once they hit old age, they start living like dogs. "(41)	"Ular qarigach, itdek yashay boshlashadi ". (52)
他的讲述像鸟爪抓住树枝那样紧紧抓住我。(32)	His story grabbed me in the same way the talons of an eagle clutch the branches of a tree. (42)	Uning hikoyasi tirnoqlarini o'ljasiga botirib olgan burgutdek o'ziga asir qilib olgandi meni. (52)
家珍一走就等于是削掉了一个角。(33)	When Jiazhen left it was like cutting off a corner. (42)	Jiashen bizni tashlab ketgan kun stolning bir burchagi kesilgandi. (54)
滑溜溜的像是穿上了鼻涕做的衣服。(35)	It felt like I was wearing clothes made of snot. (46)	Xuddi shilliqqurtning so'lagidan qilingan kiyim kiygandek bo'ldim. (60)
像只夜里的麻雀一样让连长瞄准。(42)	Like a sparrow in the night he let the commander take his aim. (56)	Qo'mondonning tepkini bosishini kutayotgan o'ljaga o'xshardi. (73)
像是赶庙会一样。(46)	it looked like a temple fair (60)	go'yoki butxona tartib- qoidalarini bajarayotgandek ko'rinardi. (76)
下面的国军就跟蚂蚁似的密密麻麻地拥来拥去。(47)	The Nationalist troops below crowded together like a colony of ants. (61)	Milliy birliklar mo'rmaxalday birjoyga to'planib olishardi. (78)
声音低得像蚊虫在叫。(50)	That voice was so soft it seemed like a mosquito buzzing back and forth around my face. (68)	Uning sasi shunchalar past ediki, qulog'imning atrofida chivin uchib yurganga o'xshardi. (87)

<p>跑到我们近前找一块空地，喊一、二、三，喊到三时将担架一翻，倒垃圾似的将伤号扔到地上就不管了。(page 70)</p>	<p>“One, two, three.” When they got to three they’d turn the stretchers over as if they were dumping out garbage”. (Page 66)</p>	<p>"Qani, bir, ikki, uch!". Uch degach, zambilni ag'darib, jarohat olganlarni go'yoki axlat to'kkandek yerga uloqtirishardi. (85-bet)</p>
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1. **"我如同一只乱飞的麻雀。"** (4)

"I was like a sparrow soaring recklessly."

"Insizqolganchumchuqdaykezibuyardim."

The metaphor "乱飞的麻雀" (a sparrow flying chaotically) symbolizes instability and aimlessness. The English translation, "soaring recklessly," preserves the original meaning, though "soaring" may also imply freedom. In Uzbek, the phrase "insiz qolgan chumchuqday" (like an abandoned sparrow) retains the connotation of loneliness and disorientation, adapting the metaphor to a culturally understandable expression.⁵

2. **"我丈人当时的脸就和松花蛋一样"** (9)

"As I asked, my father-in-law's face would look like a preserved egg."

"Ungashundaydeganimdaqaynotamningyuziburishibketardi."

The metaphor "松花蛋" (preserved egg) is a culturally specific reference used in Chinese to describe an aged or wrinkled facial expression. While the English translation maintains the metaphor, its meaning might be unclear to those unfamiliar with preserved eggs. The Uzbek translation omits the metaphor and instead directly conveys the intended meaning with "yuzi burishib ketar" (his face wrinkled), ensuring clarity and naturalness in the target language.

3. **"看着凤霞哭，我心里就跟刀割一样。"** (21)

"Seeing Fengxia cry was like having a knife pierce my heart."

"Fengxiyaningbuholiniko'rib, qalbimgaxanjarsanchilgandekbo'ldi."

The phrase "刀割" (like being cut by a knife) effectively conveys deep emotional pain. The English translation, "having a knife pierce my heart," closely follows the original, maintaining both the imagery and emotional intensity. The Uzbek

⁵Zhang, H. (2010). Metaphor and Cultural Identity in Chinese Literature. Beijing University Press.

translation intensifies the metaphor by using "qalbimgaxanjarsanchilgandek" (as if a dagger was stabbed into my heart), which enhances the dramatic effect while preserving the original meaning.

4. "就过来一长串担架，喊一、二、三，喊到三时将担架一翻，倒垃圾似的将伤号扔到地上就不管了。" (70)

"One, two, three." When they got to three, they'd turn the stretchers over as if they were dumping out garbage."

"Qani, bir, ikki, uch! Uchdegach, zambilniag'darib, jarohatolganlarnigo'yoaxlatto'kkandekyergauloqtirishardi."

The phrase "倒垃圾似的" (as if dumping out garbage) highlights the inhumane treatment of the wounded. The English translation retains the metaphor with "dumping out garbage," ensuring the original meaning is conveyed. The Uzbek translation, "go'yoaxlatto'kkandek," maintains the same level of harshness and dehumanization, preserving the strong emotional impact of the original.

Metaphors undergo various transformations in translation due to linguistic and cultural differences.

Direct equivalence is preferred when metaphors have universal meanings, but cultural substitution is necessary for culturally bound metaphors.

The loss of metaphorical meaning is a major challenge in translation, requiring careful adaptation strategies.

Future research should explore metaphor translation in other literary works to refine translation strategies further.

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